

EuCNC & 6G Summit COREnect Workshop “Hardware Enabling Technologies for 6G Networks”

Date: **Tuesday, 8 June 2021, 14:00-15:30/16:00-17:30 CEST**

Programme available at: <https://www.eucnc.eu/workshops/workshop-2/>

EUCNC | 6G Summit

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On the Road to 6G

eucnc.eu

Organizers

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Patrick Pype (NXP Semiconductors)
Frederic Giancesello (STMicroelectronics)
Patrick Cogez (AENEAS)
Colin Willcock (The 5GIA)

Scope

The COREnect project is bringing together the most prominent European industrial and academia players as well as industry associations in the network, microelectronics and verticals domains to jointly develop a high-level strategic roadmap of core subsystem and component technologies for supporting future connectivity. The goal is to establish a sustainable European technology sovereignty in 5th Generation (5G) and beyond, promote innovation and business opportunities e.g. for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), pave the way for one or more future European champions in this area, and lay a solid foundation for the long-term success of both industries.

Based on the initially identified COREnect end-to-end system view with a value chain consideration, COREnect has organised three Expert Groups (EGs) to address the three strategic focus areas within the industry roadmap:

- Expert Group #1 Computing/Storage Core Technologies for Future network.
- Expert Group #2 Communications/Sensing Core Technologies for Future network.
- Expert Group #3 Peripheral Core Technologies for Future network.

The purpose of this workshop is to present the key findings of these EGs to a broad ICT audience. Combining insights and expertise from the communication and microelectronics domain, the three expert groups will address three key areas and share their sector-specific views points on: a) Electronics for Trustworthy Communication (6G and beyond), b) Future Core Technologies and Integration and c) Energy-efficient, Green Communication Electronics.

As the EuCNC is a major event that attracts all key European stakeholders, it offers a unique opportunity to disseminate these findings as the results of almost one year of activities but also allow the exchange of ideas and opinions from the participants from the telecommunications’ sector. Towards this end, the Workshop will schedule a dedicated panel that will operate as an interactive event with the participants.

Agenda

Workshop Moderator: **Jacques Magen** (Australo).

14:00-15:30 Presentations

- **Colin Willcock**, 5GIA, “Hardware enabling technologies to ensure EU’s digital autonomy in 6G networks: The COREnect approach”.
- **Patrick Pype**, NXP, “Electronics for Trustworthy Communication (6G and beyond)”.
- **Piet Wambacq**, IMEC, “Future Core Technologies and Integration”.

Coffee Break

16:00-17:30 Presentations and Panel

- **Gerhard Fettweis**, TU Dresden, “Energy Efficient, Green Communications Electronics”
- Panel: “Opportunities and Challenges for hardware enabling technologies in the SNS Partnership”.
 - Moderator: **Yaning Zou**, TU Dresden, Technical Manager, COREnect.
 - Panelists: **Fredrik Tillman** (Ericsson), **Mohand Achouche** (Nokia), **Alexandros Kaloxylos** (5G IA), **Patrick Cogez** (AENEAS), **Ludger Verweyen** (Infineon Technologies), **Frank Hoffman** (Bosch), **Guillaume Vivier** (Sequans).